

PERCEPTION OF ANESTHESIA, SURGERY DOCTORS AND OPERATING THEATRE STAFF ABOUT MUSIC IN OPERATING ROOM

Dr. Muhammad Awais Anwar^{*1}, Dr. Adeel Ur Rehman², Dr. Sameera Saleem³,
Dr. Asma Akhtar⁴, Dr. Abdul Saboor⁵, Dr. Lubabah⁶

^{*1}MBBS, Resident FCPS Anesthesiology, Indus Hospital and Health Network

²MBBS, MCPS Anesthesiology, FCPS Anesthesiology, Supervisor, Consultant, Head of Department of Anesthesiology, Indus Hospital and Health Network

³MBBS, Resident MCPS Anesthesiology, Indus Hospital and Health Network

^{4,5,6}MBBS, Resident FCPS Anesthesiology, Indus Hospital and Health Network

^{*1}doctorawaisanwar96@gmail.com

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Corresponding Author: *

Dr. Muhammad Awais Anwar

Abstract

OBJECTIVE

To assess the perception of anaesthesia, surgery doctors and operation theatre staff about music in the operating room at Indus Hospital Karachi.

STUDY DESIGN

Cross-sectional

PLACE OF DURATION OF THE STUDY

This research was executed at the Operation Theatre Complex of Indus Hospital, Karachi from

31st July 2023 to 30th July 2024

METHODOLOGY

A total of 94 participants aged 20–45 years, including anaesthesia and surgery doctors and operation theatre technicians with ≥ 1 year experience, were recruited through non-probability consecutive sampling. Perceptions regarding music were assessed using a 10-item Likert scale questionnaire. Data were analysed using frequencies, percentages, mean and Chi-square and independent t-tests ($p \leq 0.05$).

RESULT

The mean age was 30.76 ± 6.56 years, with 58 (61.7%) males. Most reported positive perceptions, with 51 (54.2%) agreeing music improved work enjoyment, while 55 (58.5%) reported impaired communication and 56 (59.6%) increased noise. No significant gender differences in perceptions ($p > 0.05$), except higher male experience (5.10 ± 4.24 vs 3.44 ± 2.64 years; $p = 0.038$).

CONCLUSION

The perceptions of operating theatre staff regarding intraoperative music were mixed, reflecting both improved work experience and potential impairment in communication and increased background noise. These findings have important implications for patient safety and team dynamics. Institutions should adopt context-specific guidelines for music use rather than a uniform approach. Further

multi-centre studies with objective measures of communication and performance are needed to strengthen the evidence base.

INTRODUCTION

Music is a universal language, which cuts across cultures and social boundaries. It is capable of stimulating people, reducing stress, and improving their moods. Knowledge, perception and utilisation of music are important aspects in healthcare settings, especially in the demanding conditions in the operating theatre (OT) environment that should exploit the potential benefits [1]. The use of music in the operating room has become the subject of growing attention given the possible impact it may have on the patients and the healthcare workers. Surgery patients tend to be very anxious, particularly when the waiting period prior to the surgery is in progress. The use of sedatives and elaborate explanations to alleviate anxiety has long been used by the anaesthetists, but nowadays, with the introduction of the fast-acting anaesthetic and analgesic drugs, the over-use of heavy sedation has been reduced, and therefore, exploring the nonpharmacological interventions may be employed, like the use of music therapy [2-4].

Several studies have shown that music can potentially decrease preoperative anxiety and increase patient comfort and recoveries. Also, it has been linked with a lower perception of pain and a reduction of fatigue in patients, and the overall perioperative experience is improved [5-7]. In the eyes of healthcare professionals, music can also serve as a stress-reducing system, which could have a better effect on mood, focus, and performance of tasks during surgery operations [8-10].

With all these advantages, the operating theatre is a high-stress and dynamic working environment, in which distractions might pose a significant influence on communication and workflow. Distracting factors encompass too much noise of surgical equipment, alarms, pagers, and the irrelevant selections of staff [11-13]. These disturbances can be followed by miscommunication, delays in processes, and

undermined patient safety. Research has observed distractions to be common in surgeries, observing that there are several interruptions in a surgery, especially because of equipment problems and unnecessary communication [14-15].

The purpose of music in this environment is a controversial one. Whereas other professionals in the medical field see music as helpful in alleviating stress and improving productivity, there are those who feel that music can be a source of distraction and thus disrupt communication and focus, particularly in situations that necessitate a great deal of accuracy [16-17]. Moreover, there is variability in the frequency and the kind of music which is used to operate the theatres, and this is based on the different individual preferences and the practices within the institutions. Despite growing international evidence, data from Pakistan and South Asia on operating theatre staff perceptions of intraoperative music remain limited. Given regional differences in clinical settings, local evidence is essential. Therefore, this study aimed to assess the perceptions of anaesthesia providers, surgeons, and operating theatre staff regarding music in the operating room and its impact on workflow and communication.

METHODOLOGY

A cross-sectional study was conducted after obtaining approval from the ERC Board of the hospital and the CPSP, and written informed consent was obtained from all participants prior to inclusion. The study population comprised anaesthesia and surgery doctors, as well as operation theatre and anaesthesia technicians working in the operation theatre, selected through nonprobability consecutive sampling. Participants of either gender aged between 20-45 years, having at least one year of working experience in the operation theatre and willing to participate were included, while those who refused consent and healthcare workers not directly working in the

operation theatre, including nurses, porters, cleaners, sweepers and post-anaesthesia care unit staff, were excluded. Perception regarding music in the operating theatre was defined as the response to a structured questionnaire consisting of ten items adapted from previously published studies, with each response scored on a five-point Likert scale ranging from strongly disagree to strongly agree, and each question was analysed individually. The sample size of 94 participants was calculated using an anticipated prevalence of 27%¹⁰, a margin of error of 9%, and a confidence level of 95%. Data were collected by the principal investigator, using a predesigned, self-administered questionnaire that also recorded demographic variables including as age, gender, designation and years of experience; all respondents who fulfilled the inclusion criteria were approached in the operation theatre where the study purpose was explained and questionnaires given out and finally collected back after completion and all data were recorded in a structured proforma. Data analysed using SPSS v26.0 included age, gender, designation, experience and perception responses using frequencies, percentages, mean, Chi-square and Independent t-tests, with $p \leq 0.05$ considered significant.

RESULTS

Table I presents total of 94 participants were included in the study. The mean age of the participants was 30.76 ± 6.56 years, while the mean duration of experience was 4.47 ± 3.78 years. Gender distribution, the majority were male (58, 61.7%), while 36 (38.3%) were female. Regarding professional designation, anaesthetists (33, 35.1%) and surgeons (32, 34.0%) constituted the largest groups, followed by OT technicians (18, 19.1%) and anaesthesia technicians (10, 10.6%), whereas only 1 (1.1%) participant belonged to other categories.

Table II illustrates that participants demonstrated varied perceptions regarding the effects of music in the operating theatre. Regarding distraction (Q1), a considerable proportion of participants disagreed (31, 33.0%) or mildly disagreed (16,

17.0%) that music is distracting, while 36 (38.3%) either agreed or strongly agreed. For performance (Q2), participants disagreed (35, 37.2%) that they can perform better with music, and 46 (48.9%) stated that they do agree or strongly agree. Similarly, team performance (Q3), 33 (35.1%) participants said that they do not agree that music enhances team performance, and 40 (42.6%) said that they agree or strongly agree. In terms of work enjoyment (Q4), more than half of the participants (51, 54.2%) agreed or strongly agreed that music enhances their work experience. Regarding theatre list overruns (Q5), responses were mixed, with 43 (45.7%) agreeing or strongly agreeing and 27 (28.7%) disagreeing. For background noise (Q6), a majority (56, 59.6%) agreed or strongly agreed that music increases background noise in the operating theatre. Similarly, for non-work-related discussions (Q7), over half of the participants (51, 54.4%) agreed or strongly agreed that music encourages such interactions. Concerning communication (Q8), 55 (58.5%) participants agreed or strongly agreed that music affects communication between staff. Regarding the patient anxiety (Q9) question, the answers were mixed, with 42 (44.7%) agreeing or strongly agreeing that music helps reduce patient anxiety, while 29 (30.9%) disagreed. Finally, for familiarity (Q10), 40 (42.6%) participants agreed or strongly agreed that music creates a sense of familiarity in the operating theatre, whereas 24 (25.5%) disagreed.

Table III, the mean age of the male participants was 31.36 ± 7.04 years, and the mean age of the female ones was 29.78 ± 5.67 years with no statistically significant difference between the two groups ($p=0.258$). However, male participants had significantly higher experience (5.10 ± 4.24 years) compared to females (3.44 ± 2.64 years; $p=0.038$). For Q1, 10 (17.2%) males and 9 (25.0%) females agreed, while 8 (13.8%) males and 9 (25.0%) females strongly agreed that music is distracting; however, the difference was not statistically significant ($p=0.128$). Regarding Q2, 16 (27.6%) males and 11 (30.6%) females agreed, and 15 (25.9%) males and 4 (11.1%) females strongly agreed that they perform better with music,

whereas 20 (34.5%) males and 15 (41.7%) females disagreed, showing no significant difference ($p=0.529$). For Q3, 12 (20.7%) males and 8 (22.2%) females agreed, and 15 (25.9%) males and 5 (13.9%) females strongly agreed that team performance improves with music; however, 17 (29.3%) males and 16 (44.4%) females disagreed, with no significant association ($p=0.467$). Regarding Q4, 17 (29.3%) males and 13 (36.1%) females agreed, while 17 (29.3%) males and 4 (11.1%) females strongly agreed that music improves work enjoyment, with no significant difference ($p=0.309$). For Q5, 23 (39.7%) males and 10 (27.8%) females agreed, while 9 (15.5%) males and 1 (2.8%) female strongly agreed that music reduces theatre list overruns; however, no significant difference was observed ($p=0.114$). Regarding Q6, 19 (32.8%) males and 15 (41.7%) females agreed, and 14 (24.1%) males and 8 (22.2%) females strongly agreed that music increases background noise, with no statistically

significant difference ($p=0.262$). For Q7, 18 (31.0%) males and 16 (44.4%) females agreed, while 11 (19.0%) males and 6 (16.7%) females strongly agreed that music encourages non-work-related discussions, showing no significant association ($p=0.674$). Regarding Q8, 21 (36.2%) males and 15 (41.7%) females agreed, and 10 (17.2%) males and 9 (25.0%) females strongly agreed that music affects communication, with no significant difference ($p=0.773$). For Q9, 19 (32.8%) males and 9 (25.0%) females agreed, while 9 (15.5%) males and 5 (13.9%) females strongly agreed that music reduces patient anxiety; however, 15 (25.9%) males and 14 (38.9%) females disagreed, with no significant difference ($p=0.277$). Finally, for Q10, 15 (25.9%) males and 11 (30.6%) females agreed, and 12 (20.7%) males and 3 (5.6%) females strongly agreed that music creates a sense of familiarity, with no statistically significant difference ($p=0.245$).

Table I: Baseline Characteristics of Study Participants (n=94)		
Mean ± Standard Deviation		95% Confidence Interval
Age in years = 30.76 ± 6.56		29.41–32.10
Experience in years = 4.47 ± 3.78		3.69–5.24
Frequency %		
Gender	Male	58 (61.7)
	Female	36 (38.3)
Designation	Anaesthetist	33 (35.1)
	OT Technician	18 (19.1)
	Surgeon	32 (34.0)
	Anaesthesia Technician	10 (10.6)

	Others	1 (1.1)			
Table II: Distribution of participants' responses regarding the effects of music in the operating theatre (n= 94)					
Q1: Music in the operating theatre is distracting	Frequency %				
	Agree	Strongly agree	Disagree	Mildly Disagree	Cannot say
	19 (20.2)	17 (18.1)	31 (33.0)	16 (17.0)	11 (11.7)
Q2: I perform better when music is played in the operating theatre	Agree	Strongly agree	Disagree	Mildly Disagree	Cannot say
	27 (28.7)	19 (20.2)	35 (37.2)	6 (6.4)	7 (7.4)
	Q3: Team performance improves when music is played in the operating theatre	Agree	Strongly agree	Disagree	Mildly Disagree
20 (21.3)		20 (21.3)	33 (35.1)	13 (13.8)	8 (8.5)
Q4: I enjoy my work more when music is played in the operating theatre		Agree	Strongly agree	Disagree	Mildly Disagree
	30 (31.9)	21 (22.3)	27 (28.7)	10 (10.6)	6 (6.4)
	Q5: Music reduces the likelihood of theatre list overruns	Agree	Strongly agree	Disagree	Mildly Disagree
33 (35.1)		10 (10.6)	27 (28.7)	12 (12.8)	12 (12.8)
Q6: Music increases background noise in the operating theatre		Agree	Strongly agree	Disagree	Mildly Disagree
	34 (36.2)	22 (23.4)	23 (24.5)	12 (12.8)	3 (3.2)

Q7: Music encourages nonwork-related discussions among staff	Agree	Strongly agree	Disagree	Mildly Disagree	Cannot say
	34 (36.3)	17 (18.1)	23 (24.5)	16 (17.0)	4 (4.3)
Q8: Music affects communication between staff	Agree	Strongly agree	Disagree	Mildly Disagree	Cannot say
	36 (38.3)	19 (20.2)	19 (20.2)	17 (18.1)	3 (3.2)
Q9: Music reduces patient anxiety before anaesthesia	Agree	Strongly agree	Disagree	Mildly Disagree	Cannot say
	28 (29.8)	14 (14.9)	29 (30.9)	5 (5.3)	18 (19.1)
Q10: Music creates a sense of familiarity in the operating theatre	Agree	Strongly agree	Disagree	Mildly Disagree	Cannot say
	26 (27.7)	14 (14.9)	24 (25.5)	16 (17.0)	14 (14.9)

Table III: Comparison of perceptions regarding music in the operating theatre between male and female participants (n= 94)

Characteristics and Perceptions	Gender		P-Value	
	Male (n=58)	Female (n=36)		
Age in years	31.36 ± 7.04	29.78 ± 5.67	0.258	
Experience in years	5.10 ± 4.24	3.44 ± 2.64	0.038	
Q1: Music in the operating theatre is distracting	Agree	10 (17.2)	9 (25.0)	0.128
	Strongly agree	8 (13.8)	9 (25.0)	
	Disagree	22 (37.9)	9 (25.0)	
	Mildly Disagree	13 (22.4)	3 (8.3)	
	Cannot say	5 (8.6)	6 (16.7)	
	Agree	16 (27.6)	11 (30.6)	0.529

Q2: I perform better when music is played in the operating theatre	Strongly agree	15 (25.9)	4 (11.1)	
	Disagree	20 (34.5)	15 (41.7)	
	Mildly Disagree	3 (5.2)	3 (8.3)	
	Cannot say	4 (6.9)	3 (8.3)	
Q3: Team performance improves when music is played in the operating theatre	Agree	12 (20.7)	8 (22.2)	0.467
	Strongly agree	15 (25.9)	5 (13.9)	
	Disagree	17 (29.3)	16 (44.4)	
	Mildly Disagree	8 (13.8)	5 (13.9)	
	Cannot say	6 (10.3)	2 (5.6)	
Q4: I enjoy my work more when music is played in the operating theatre	Agree	17 (29.3)	13 (36.1)	0.309
	Strongly agree	17 (29.3)	4 (11.1)	
	Disagree	14 (24.1)	13 (36.1)	
	Mildly Disagree	6 (10.3)	4 (11.1)	
	Cannot say	4 (6.9)	2 (5.6)	
Q5: Music reduces the likelihood of theatre list overruns	Agree	23 (39.7)	10 (27.8)	0.114
	Strongly agree	9 (15.5)	1 (2.8)	
	Disagree	15 (25.9)	12 (33.3)	
	Mildly Disagree	5 (8.6)	7 (19.4)	
	Cannot say	6 (10.3)	6 (10.3)	
Q6: Music increases background noise in the operating theatre	Agree	19 (32.8)	15 (41.7)	0.262
	Strongly agree	14 (24.1)	8 (22.2)	
	Disagree	18 (31.0)	5 (13.9)	
	Mildly Disagree	5 (8.6)	7 (19.4)	
	Cannot say	2 (3.4)	1 (2.8)	
Q7: Music encourages nonwork-related discussions among staff	Agree	18 (31.0)	16 (44.4)	0.674
	Strongly agree	11 (19.0)	6 (16.7)	
	Disagree	16 (27.6)	7 (19.4)	
	Mildly Disagree	11 (19.0)	5 (13.9)	
	Cannot say	2 (3.4)	2 (5.6)	
	Agree	21 (36.2)	15 (41.7)	0.773

Q8: Music affects communication between staff	Strongly agree	10 (17.2)	9 (25.0)	
	Disagree	13 (22.4)	6 (16.7)	
	Mildly Disagree	12 (20.7)	5 (13.9)	
	Cannot say	2 (3.4)	1 (2.8)	
Q9: Music reduces patient anxiety before anaesthesia	Agree	19 (32.8)	9 (25.0)	0.277
	Strongly agree	9 (15.5)	5 (13.9)	
	Disagree	15 (25.9)	14 (38.9)	
	Mildly Disagree	5 (8.6)	0 (0.0)	
	Cannot say	10 (17.2)	8 (22.2)	
Q10: Music creates a sense of familiarity in the operating theatre	Agree	15 (25.9)	11 (30.6)	0.245
	Strongly agree	12 (20.7)	3 (5.6)	
	Disagree	12 (20.7)	12 (33.3)	
	Mildly Disagree	11 (19.0)	5 (13.9)	
	Cannot say	8 (13.8)	6 (16.7)	

DISCUSSION

Operating theatre (OT) is a high stakes clinical setting in which strong communication, focus, and collaboration are critical to patient safety and efficiency of the process. Incorporation of nonpharmacological adjunctive like music adds a complex dynamic, providing possible psychological benefits and at the same time, giving rise to a distraction risk and impaired communication. Such duality renders the perception of music among the OT staff a clinically relevant and operationally significant phenomenon, especially in the challenging surgical environments.

In the current study, the group of participants showed a diversified perception of the use of music in the OT and heterogeneity in terms of both facilitative and disruptive facets. A significant proportion (54.2%) of respondents accepted the fact that music increased work satisfaction, which aligns with the literature that music decreases occupational stress and improves the moods of surgical staff [7,8]. Nonetheless, this perceived advantage was offset by results that 59.6%

experienced more background noise and 58.5% were experiencing impaired communication. The results indicate the natural compromise between psychological comfort and efficiency in an operationally challenging environment. The fact that the gender differences in perception are not statistically significant ($p > 0.05$), though males have a higher experience ($p = 0.038$), indicates that the influence of perception of music is probably driven by the environmental and task-related factors rather than by demographic variables.

When comparing the results by Faraj et al., who found that almost two-thirds of healthcare professionals preferred music in the operating theatre with less concerns about communication disruption, our research shows a relatively high percentage of negative attitudes, especially with communication impairment (58.5% vs. 40%). Faraj et al. also found a rather positive attitude towards music with no major problem of workflow disruption, whereas our participants rated more often the background noise increased in 59.6% compared to other study approaches indicating contextual variations in terms of OT workload,

acoustic control, and a different approach to music use [10].

Comparable findings have been reported in more recent literature. Fu et al. [6] observed that despite the well-known positive effects of music on patients, especially in calming down stressed patients, about 30-50% of the staff reported that music is a distraction during crucial surgical procedures, which is also consistent with our results who reported 38.3% of personnel concurring that music is distracting. Likewise, Ijah et al. [16] reported that nearly half of OT personnel believed music interferes with communication, which is consistent with our observation of 58.5%. Furthermore, George et al. [18] demonstrated that while background music might enhance subjective comfort, it does not favour the accuracy of communication during complex procedures, supporting our results on communication interference. Furthermore, the qualitative results of Weldon et al. [19] reveal that music can disrupt verbal interactions and coordination within a team, especially during the high-risk surgical stages that need accurate communication. This supports our finding that more than half of participants perceived music as affecting communication. Similarly, Narayanan A et al. [20] in their systematic review concluded that while music could change the surgeon mood and decrease stress, its effect on technical performance and team communication was irregular and context-dependent, which also supported the ambivalent perceptions that observe in our study. From a physiologically and cognitively, music can produce its positive effects by regulating the autonomic nervous system by decreasing sympathetic activity, which will consequently relieve stress and burnout in healthcare professionals [7]. This aligns with findings from Siu et al. [14], which demonstrate show that noise is capable of causing impairment of communication and task performance, and hence it is a plausible explanation that stimulated more perception of distraction and communication impairment.

The strengths of the study are that a multidisciplinary cohort consisting of anaesthetists, surgeons, and OT technicians has

been considered, which gives the opportunity to assess multiple perceptions of the various professional roles. Furthermore, the application of a structured and validated Likert-scale questionnaire also allowed objective measurement of subjective perceptions, which could be easily compared with existing literature.

This study has several limitations. Being a single-centre study, the findings may have limited generalisability to other healthcare settings with different institutional practices. The relatively small sample size may reduce statistical power and limit subgroup analyses. The use of nonprobability consecutive sampling introduces the possibility of selection bias. Additionally, the cross-sectional design precludes causal inference. The type, volume, and timing of music were not standardised, which may have influenced individual perceptions. Furthermore, multiple Chisquare tests were performed across gender-stratified perception items without adjustment for multiple comparisons, which may increase the risk of type I error. Therefore, statistically significant findings, particularly for experience ($p = 0.038$), should be interpreted with caution as exploratory rather than confirmatory.

CONCLUSION

The perceptions of operating theatre staff regarding intraoperative music were mixed, reflecting both improved work experience and potential impairment in communication and increased background noise. These findings have important implications for patient safety and team dynamics. Institutions should adopt context-specific guidelines for music use rather than a uniform approach. Further multi-centre studies with objective measures of communication and performance are needed to strengthen the evidence base.

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